

SYNTHESIS OF THE 6-METHOXY/HYDROXY SUBSTITUTED 7-ACETYL-2-ADAMANTYL-5-BROMOBENZOFURANS AS HAVING POTENTIAL ANTIHYPERGLYCEMIC AND ANTIOXIDANT PROPERTIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20082610>**Abstract**

A library of 7-acetyl-2-adamantyl-5-bromo-6-methoxybenzo[b]furans **2a–c** was synthesized and converted to the corresponding ortho-(hydroxyacetyl)-substituted 2-adamantyl-benzo[b]furan derivatives **3a–c**. Adamantane derivatives (1-ethynyladamantane, 1-(4-ethynylphenyl)adamantane, and 2-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)adamantane) were used as terminal alkynes in the Sonogashira reaction. The structures of both series of compounds were characterized using a combination of spectroscopic methods.

Keywords: 7-acetyl-2-adamantyl-5-bromo-6-(methoxy/hydroxy), benzofurans, 2-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)adamantane, 1-(4-ethynylphenyl)adamantane, 1-ethynyladamantane.

Introduction

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) has become one of the leading medical challenges of the 21st century due to the association of this metabolic disorder with cancer, cardiovascular disease, stroke, and neurodegenerative disorders [1]. This disease is characterized by defective insulin secretion and insulin resistance in its target organs [2], which are attributed to elevated blood glucose levels known as postprandial hyperglycemia (PPG) [3]. PPG has emerged as a prominent and early event in T2DM. Various studies have established that pancreatic α -amylase and intestinal α -glucosidase are among the key metabolic targets associated with the onset and progression of this metabolic disorder [4]. Phenolic compounds such as hydroxy and/or alkoxy-substituted acetophenones of natural and synthetic origin [5] and their benzofuran derivatives [6–8] continue to attract considerable interest in medicinal chemistry in the context of antidiabetic and anticancer drug development. For example, 3,5-dibromo-2,4-dihydroxyacetophenone I and its ether derivatives II (R = alkyl- or aryl), shown in Fig. 1, have previously been found to exhibit potent anti- α -glucosidase activity compared to acarbose (IC₅₀ = 54.74 ± 0.16 μM) with IC₅₀ values in the range of 1.68 ± 0.05–7.88 ± 0.17 μM [9]. Similarly, similar 2-acylbenzofurans have been found to inhibit α -glucosidase [10]. 2-Unsubstituted 5-acetyl-4-hydroxybenzofuran derivatives III and IV have previously shown inhibitory effects against PTP1B activity, which is also implicated in the pathogenesis and progression of T2DM [11]. Inhibition of this intracellular non-receptor protein tyrosine phosphatase increases insulin sensitivity and glucose uptake, as well as energy

expenditure, making it a potential target for the treatment of obesity [12]. Several natural 2-arylbenzofuran derivatives isolated from *Morus alba* root bark have also been found to inhibit PTP1B activity [13]. A series of similar 5-acetyl-2-aryl-6-hydroxybenzo[b]furans V were prepared and evaluated by in vitro enzymatic assays for inhibitory effects against α -glucosidase, PTP1B, and β -secretase [14]. Euparin (1-(6-hydroxy-2-isopropenyl-1-benzofuran-5-yl)-1-ethanone) VI and furostipitol (5-actyl-6-hydroxy-2-(2-hydroxyisopropyl)-4-methoxybenzofuran) VII were isolated from the roots of *Petasites hybridus* [15] and the stem bark of *Melicope stipitate* [16], respectively. Compound VI exhibited cytotoxicity and apoptotic effects on breast cancer cell line (MCF-7) [15]. Prenylated benzofuran derivatives VIII (faberions I–IV) were isolated from the whole *Hypericum faberi* plant together with prenylated acylphloroglucinols [17,18]. Among these compounds, faberion II (R1 = s-Bu, R2 = H) and faberion III (R1 = i-Pr, R2 = OH) showed moderate cytotoxicity against pancreatic cell line (PANC-1) with IC₅₀ values of 6.2 μM and 9.0 μM, respectively. 2-(4-benzyloxy-3-methoxyphenyl)-5-(carbethoxyethylene)-7-methoxybenzofuran IX, which is an intermediate in the total synthesis of ailantoidol, was found to suppress the proliferation and metastasis effects in P53-mutated hepatocellular carcinoma cells [19]. Structure-activity relationship (SAR) of substituted benzofuran derivatives revealed that the presence of bromine atom in the fused benzene ring invariably resulted in a significant enhancement of the anticancer properties [20–23].

R = 1-Ad (a), Ad-4-Ph- (b), 2-AdCH₂- (c)
Ad - = adamantyl

Scheme 1. Sonogashira cross-coupling of 1 and demethylation of 2 to 3.

Fig. 1. Chemical structures of halogenated ortho-hydroxyacetophenones, ortho-(hydroxyacetyl)- and carbethoxy-substituted benzofurans and target derivatives X.

We examined the antidiabetic properties of bromo-substituted hydroxyacetophenones I and II and benzofuran derivatives III–V, as well as the cytotoxicity of naturally occurring compounds VI, VIII (R₁ = Et, R₂ = H), and IX, and decided to synthesize adamantyl analogs of the generalized chemical structure X. The

lone pair of electrons on bromine and the positively charged region on this atom, called the σ -hole, are known to facilitate hydrogen and halogen bond interactions with amino acid residues in receptors, respectively, stabilizing drug-receptor interactions [21].

On the other hand, the lipophilic adamantyl moiety is known to enhance the membrane-penetrating properties of phenolic compounds, resulting in improved aqueous solubility, easier absorption, and increased oral bioavailability with reduced toxic side effects [22,23]. Moreover, the main alkoxy group is prone to demethylation in vitro and in vivo [18,23]. This makes anisole derivatives potential prodrugs for oxidative metabolism by cytochrome P450 enzymes to provide a pool from which the most active phenolic metabolites can be released in vivo. In the case of the target 6-methoxy-substituted benzofurans, the resulting ortho-hydroxycarbonyl moiety is proposed to participate in intramolecular hydrogen bonding interactions to form a thermodynamically favorable six-membered structure [14]. This conformationally locked heterocyclic ring structure tends to facilitate favorable alignment of small drug molecules with protein pockets [24], resulting in increased solubility, lipophilicity, membrane permeability, and potency or affinity of the ligand for the target [25–27]. Our design strategy involved using 5-bromo-2-hydroxy-3-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone as a template for a site-selective palladium-catalyzed Sonogashira tandem cross-coupling to construct the benzofuran scaffold. Demethylation of the resulting 7-acetyl-2-adamantyl-5-bromo-6-methoxybenzofurans is predicted to yield conformationally locked ortho-(hydroxyacetyl)benzofuran derivatives. The target compounds are analogs of V with a linear conformation between the intramolecular hydrogen-bonded ortho-hydroxyacetyl moiety and the 2-adamantylbenzofuran skeleton [14].

Materials and Methods

The chemical reagents and solvents used in this study were obtained from Merck Ltd and used without further purification. Melting points (mp) of the synthesized compounds were recorded on a Boetius stage. IR spectra were recorded using the thin film method and in KBr pellets on a Bruker Alpha spectrometer. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AM300 spectrometer (300 and 75 MHz, respectively) in DMSO- d_6 and CDCl_3 at 25 °C.

Chemical shifts are reported relative to tetramethylsilane (TMS), used as an internal standard ($\delta = 0.00$ ppm). Reaction progress and purity monitoring were performed by TLC on Merck Silicagel 60 F254 plates, eluent toluene. The synthesis and analytical data of 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone have been published in the literature [28]. 1-Ethynyladamantane and 2-(prop-2-yn-1-yl)adamantane were obtained from Enamine Ltd. 1-(4-Ethynylphenyl)adamantane was obtained from AKos GmbH.

5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-3-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone (1).

A solution of 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone (5.0 g, 17.1 mmol) in acetic acid (50 mL) was treated with N-bromosuccinimide (3.1 g, 17.1 mmol). The mixture was stirred at reflux for 1.5 h and then neutralized with ice-cold saturated aqueous sodium thiosulfate. The precipitate was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol, yielding (1) as brown crystals (7.66 g, 76%). M.p. 101–104 °C. IR (cm^{-1}): 623, 680, 829, 942, 1061, 1202, 1281, 1360, 1408, 1558, 1603, 2947; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 2.78 (s, 3H,

$-\text{CH}_3$), 3.91 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 8.11 (s, 1H, H-5), 13.59 (s, 1H, OH); ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 31.8, 62.1, 81.4, 107.2, 116.1, 147.6, 159.2, 161.7, 204.3.2.3.

General procedure for the synthesis of (2a–c).

A mixture of (1) (2.70 mmol), $\text{PdCl}_2(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (10% of (1)), CuI (10% of (1)), and Cs_2CO_3 (3.5 equiv. of (1)) in 2:1 dioxane:H $_2\text{O}$ (v/v, 30 mL) in a two-necked flask equipped with a condenser was purged with argon for 20 min. An argon-filled balloon was connected to the top of the condenser. Phenylacetylene (1.5 equiv. of (2a)) was added, and the mixture was stirred at 115 °C for 6 h. The reaction mixture was poured into ice water, and the product was extracted with chloroform. The combined organic layers were washed with NaCl brine and dried over MgSO_4 . The solvent was evaporated on a rotary evaporator. The residue was purified by column chromatography on silica gel with using toluene as eluent, yielding (2a) as a light brown solid. Compounds (2a–c) were prepared by this method.

1-(5-Bromo-6-methoxy-2-(1-adamantyl)benzofuran-7-yl)ethan-1-one (2a).

Light-brown crystals (0.52 g, 48%) M.p. 183–185 °C. IR (cm^{-1}): 516, 605, 678, 778, 833, 867, 921, 1060, 1145, 1192, 1307, 1400, 1562, 1589, 1678, 2931. NMR ^1H (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 1.76 (6CH $_2$, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 2.80 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.93 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 6.94 (s, 1H, H-3), 7.83 (s, 1H, H-4). NMR ^{13}C (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 27.8, 32.3, 33.7, 36.7, 63.5, 100.3, 113.3, 120.9, 151.2, 152.0, 158.3, 197.5.

1-(5-Bromo-6-methoxy-2-phenyl-4-(1-adamantyl)benzofuran-7-yl)ethan-1-one (2b).

Light gray crystals (0.73 g, 56%). M.p. 167–169 °C. IR (cm^{-1}): 516, 605, 678, 778, 833, 867, 921, 1060, 1145, 1192, 1307, 1400, 1562, 1589, 1678, 2931. NMR ^1H (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 1.76 (6CH $_2$, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 2.80 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.93 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 6.94 (s, 1H, H-3), 7.34–7.41 (s, 2H, H-4' and H-5'), 7.45 (t, $J = 7.6$ Hz, H-3'), 7.81 (d, $J = 7.0$ Hz, 2H, H-2',6'), 7.83 (s, 1H, H-4). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 27.8, 32.3, 33.7, 36.7, 63.5, 100.3, 113.3, 120.9, 125.2, 126.6, 127.8, 129.1, 129.4, 129.6, 151.2, 152.0, 158.3, 197.5.

1-(5-Bromo-6-methoxy-2-(2-adamantylmethyl)benzofuran-7-yl)ethan-1-one (2c).

Light yellow crystals (0.69 g, 61%). M.p. 175–177 °C. IR (cm^{-1}): 516, 605, 678, 778, 833, 867, 921, 1060, 1145, 1192, 1307, 1400, 1562, 1589, 1678, 2931. NMR ^1H (500 MHz, CDCl_3 , δ ppm): 1.76 (5CH $_2$, Ad), 1.87 (4CH, Ad), 2.00 (t, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H, $-\text{CH}_2\text{Ad}$), 2.80 (s, 3H, $-\text{CH}_3$), 3.93 (s, 3H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 6.94 (s, 1H, H-3), 7.83 (s, 1H, H-4). ^{13}C NMR (125 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 27.8, 32.3, 33.7, 36.7, 63.5, 100.3, 113.3, 120.9, 151.2, 152.0, 158.3, 197.5.

General Synthesis Procedure for (3a–c).

A solution of (2a–c) (0.579 mmol) in dichloromethane (10 mL) was cooled to 0 °C, and boron tribromide (2.0 equiv) was added. The mixture was stirred at room temperature for 3 h, monitoring by TLC. The reaction mixture was poured into ice water, and the product was extracted with chloroform. The combined organic layers were washed with aqueous NaCl solution and dried over MgSO_4 . The salt was filtered off, and the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure on a rotary evaporator. The residue was purified by column

chromatography on silica gel using toluene as eluent. Compounds (3a-c) were obtained using this procedure.

1-(5-Bromo-6-hydroxy-2-(1-adamantyl)benzofuran-7-yl)ethan-1-one (3a).

Brown crystals (2.01 g, 89%). M.p. 195–197 °C. IR (cm⁻¹): 516, 605, 678, 778, 833, 867, 921, 1060, 1145, 1192, 1307, 1400, 1562, 1589, 1678, 2931. NMR ¹H (CDCl₃, δ ppm): 1.76 (6CH₂, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 2.80 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 13.43 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.94 (s, 1H, H-3), 7.83 (s, 1H, H-4). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 27.8, 32.3, 33.7, 36.7, 63.5, 100.3, 113.3, 120.9, 151.2, 152.0, 158.3, 197.5.

1-(5-Bromo-6-hydroxy-2-phenyl-4-(1-adamantyl)benzofuran-7-yl)ethan-1-one (3b).

Light gray crystals (1.44 g, 53%). M.p. 186–188 °C. IR (cm⁻¹): 516, 605, 678, 778, 833, 867, 921, 1060, 1145, 1192, 1307, 1400, 1562, 1589, 1678, 2931. NMR ¹H (CDCl₃, δ ppm): 1.76 (6CH₂, Ad), 1.87 (3CH, Ad), 2.80 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 13.63 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.94 (s, 1H, H-3), 7.36–7.45 (s, 2H, H-4' and H-5'), 7.48 (t, J = 7.6 Hz, H-3'), 7.78 (d, J = 7.0 Hz, 2H, H-2',6'), 7.85 (s, 1H, H-4). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 27.8, 32.3, 33.7, 36.7, 63.5, 100.3, 113.3, 120.9, 125.2, 126.6, 127.8, 129.1, 129.4, 129.6, 151.2, 152.0, 158.3, 197.5.

1-(5-Bromo-6-hydroxy-2-(2-adamantylmethyl)benzofuran-7-yl)ethan-1-one (3c).

Light yellow crystals (1.57 g, 67%). M.p. 205–207 °C. IR (cm⁻¹): 516, 605, 678, 778, 833, 867, 921, 1060, 1145, 1192, 1307, 1400, 1562, 1589, 1678, 2931. NMR ¹H (CDCl₃, δ ppm): 1.76 (5CH₂, Ad), 1.87 (4CH, Ad), 2.00 (t, J = 8.0 Hz, 2H, -CH₂Ad), 2.80 (s, 3H, -CH₃), 13.93 (s, 1H, -OH), 6.94 (s, 1H, H-3), 7.83 (s, 1H, H-4). ¹³C NMR (DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 27.8, 32.3, 33.7, 36.7, 63.5, 100.3, 113.3, 120.9, 151.2, 152.0, 158.3, 197.5.3.

Results and Discussion

Synthesis and Spectroscopic Characterization of Compounds

(2) and (3).

5-Bromo-2-hydroxy-3-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone 1 [28], used as a substrate in this work, was prepared from 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone in the presence of N-bromosuccinimide as a halogenating agent in acetic acid at reflux for 1 h. Sequential halogenation of 2-hydroxy-6-methoxyacetophenone with N-iodosuccinimide in acetic acid at reflux for 1 h, followed by bromination of the intermediate 2-hydroxy-3-iodo-6-methoxyacetophenone with N-iodosuccinimide also afforded 1 in a one-pot operation. It has been confirmed that the selectivity in transition metal-mediated cross-coupling of polyhalogenated aromatic compounds is generally related to the relative strength of the Csp²-X bond (trend: C-I < C-Br < C-Cl < C-F), which allows selective cross-coupling with iodides in the presence of bromides and chlorides [42,43]. The alkynylated product in the case of the Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction of orthohalophenol derivatives can undergo in situ subsequent Kakki-type cyclization to afford benzofuran derivatives [14,18]. The mixed 3,5-dihalogenated substrate 1 was subjected to conventional Sonogashira cross-coupling conditions with phenylacetylene or alkylacetylene derivatives in the presence of a mixture of PdCl₂(PPh₃)₂-CuI catalysts and Cs₂CO₃ as base in a dioxane-water mixture (2:1, v/v)

at 115 °C for 6 h (Scheme 1). Aqueous workup and purification by silica gel column chromatography afforded in sequence in each case compounds characterized using a combination of spectroscopic methods as a homolinked dimer and a cross-coupled product (Table 1). The presence of additional peaks in the aromatic region with a singlet near δ = 7.44 ppm excluded the possibility of intermediate 3-alkynylated 2-hydroxyacetophenone derivatives and confirmed that the structures are benzofuran derivatives. 3-Alkynylated derivatives were also excluded due to the absence of a set of singlets in the regions δ = 85.0–87.0 ppm and δ = 90.0–93.0 ppm, typical for acetylene carbons.

We hypothesized that the presence of a polar -OH group would result in a favorable lipophilic potential for the entire benzofuran scaffold and achieve a better enzyme inhibition rate. Therefore, compounds 2 were demethylated with boron tribromide in dichloromethane at room temperature for 5 h. Aqueous workup and silica gel chromatography purification for substrates 2a–c yielded products characterized using a combination of NMR and IR spectroscopy as the corresponding ortho-hydroxyacetyl-substituted 2-adamantyl benzofuran derivatives 3a–c.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the demethylated derivatives (3a–3c) lacked a signal for the 6-methoxy group, but a significantly downfield-shifted singlet was detected at δ = 13.60 ppm, which integrated as a single proton and corresponded to the hydroxyl group. This resonance was observed in the ¹H NMR spectra with hydrogen bond acceptor properties. The significant downfield shift of the singlet corresponding to the 6-hydroxyl proton in the series (3a–c) is due to the intramolecular hydrogen bond interaction with the carbonyl oxygen, forming a six-membered ring.

Intramolecular hydrogen bond interaction tends to increase the O–H bond length and leads to a significant downfield shift of the proton signal in the ¹H NMR spectrum. This non-covalent bonding interaction also led to a shift of the carbonyl band for compounds 3 (1614 cm⁻¹) compared to 2 (1685 cm⁻¹). The formation of a thermodynamically favorable six-membered ring also caused a strong shift of the hydroxyl band of compounds 3 toward the region of aliphatic and/or aromatic C–H bonds (2700–3100 cm⁻¹). The center of the O–H band was difficult to determine, consistent with the definition of a strong intramolecular hydrogen bond.

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